

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

EFFECT OF NANO-MATERIAL SPRAY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF THE CF/NANO-PET COMPOSITES

Yeon-Taek Hwang, Hanyang University
Hui-Jin Um, Hanyang University
Kyung-Hee Choi, Hanyang University
Hak-Sung Kim*, Hanyang University

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Nano-material(CNT) spray on spread CF tow

- In this work, to enhance the mechanical properties of the carbon fiber reinforced composites, nano-material such as Carbon Nanotube(CNT) was applied in the manufacturing process of the composites.
- CNT dispersed ethanol solvent was sprayed on the spread CF tow (Chomarat™, 150 gsm)
- As shown in the left SEM images, CNT was well coated on the surface of the carbon fibers

Inter-laminar fracture toughness of CF/Nano-PET composites

- Mechanical properties of the CNT sprayed CF/PET composites was enhanced with the weight fraction of CNT.
- Especially, as shown in the left bar graph, inter-laminar fracture toughness was significantly increased in the 0.5 wt% CNT case.